

INFLUENCE OF α -PHENYL GROUP IN THREE CARBON
TAUTOMERISM. PART I. TAUTOMERISM OF
 α -PHENYL- α,β -, β,γ -UNSATURATED
ACIDS AND ESTERS.

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The tautomerism of substances of the general structure

where R_1 , R_2 , R_3 and R_4 are alkyl groups or portions of an alicyclic ring and X is a negative activating group like COOH, CO₂Et, COMe and CN has been extensively studied by Kon, Linstead and their collaborators. The influence of methyl and ethyl groups in different positions with respect to the activating groups on mobility and equilibrium of such systems has been investigated (Goldberg and Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2843; Kon and Linstead, *ibid.*, 1929, 1269; Kon and Thakur, *ibid.*, 1930, 2217; Kon, Linstead and Maclean, *ibid.*, 1932, 2454 etc.) and shown to be in accordance with what was to be expected theoretically from the ionic mechanism first suggested for tautomeric systems by Ingold, Shoppee and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1477) and later applied to three carbon systems of the above type in particular by Linstead (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2498). Linstead and Williams (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2565) studied γ -phenylbutenoic acids and styryl ketones and showed that γ -phenyl group stabilised $\beta\gamma$ -phase exclusively which they attributed to the conjugative effect of the phenyl group. In β -phenylhexenoic acids Kon, Linstead and Wright (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 640) found that the β -phenyl group behaved like a β -methyl group. This was in agreement with the suggestion of Linstead (*loc. cit.*) that the phenyl group in three carbon system behaves as a non-polar group, influencing the mobility and equilibrium of the system by its steric and conjugative effects.

The object of the present work was to study the effect of α -phenyl group in three carbon system terminated by an activating group like COOH and CO₂Et and to compare it with that of α -methyl group already studied by Kon and Thakur (*loc. cit.*) and Kon, Linstead and Maclean (*loc. cit.*). The methyl group as shown by the above workers

depressed the mobility of the the system and shifted the equilibrium to αβ side except in the case of ketones and ethyl α-methylcyclohexenyl acetate where the βγ-form was favoured. It was, therefore, interesting to see whether this irregular behaviour of the α-methyl group is also shown by the α-phenyl group. In the present work the tautomerism of the following compounds has been studied :

1. α-Phenylcyclohexylidene acetic acid $\rightleftharpoons$ α-Phenylcyclohexenylacetic acid.
2. α-Phenyl-Δ^a-hexenoic acid $\rightleftharpoons$ α-Phenyl-Δ^b-hexenoic acid.
3. Ethyl α-phenylcyclohexylidene acetate $\rightleftharpoons$ Ethyl α-phenylcyclohexenylacetate.
4. Ethyl α-phenyl-Δ^a-hexenoate $\rightleftharpoons$ Ethyl α-phenyl-Δ^b-hexenoate.

The mobilities and the positions of equilibrium in case of acids were determined under the standard conditions of Linstead (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2579). In case of esters the standard conditions of Kon and Linstead (*loc. cit.*) were followed. The iodometric methods of Linstead and May (*loc. cit.*) for the estimation of αβ- and βγ- unsaturated acids and esters in their mixtures were applicable in the present case.

The results are summarised in the following table, the parent acids and esters and the corresponding α-methyl acids and esters being included for comparison.

TABLE I.

Compounds. (only βγ- form shown).	Authors.	αβ-Isomeride at equilibrium. 10(K ₁ + K ₂).	Mobility
cycloHexenylacetic acid	Linstead (<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1927, 355)	12%	1
α-Methylcyclohexenylacetic acid	Kon and Thakur (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	32	0.0075
α-Phenylcyclohexenylacetic acid	Present authors	42	0.00954
Hexenoic acid	Linstead (<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1928, 2343)	77	7(?)
α-Methyl-Δ ^b -hexenoic acid	Linstead (<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1932, 2454). Kon and Maclean	88	4.882*

TABLE I (contd.).

Compounds.	Authors.	$\alpha\beta$ -Isomeride at equilibrium.	Mobility.
α -Phenyl- Δ^b -hexenoic acid	Present authors	87	0.4874
	Esters.		Mobility ($K_1 + K_2$) $\times 10^4$.
Ethyl cyclohexenyl acetate	Kon, Linstead and Mac- lennan (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	38	8.1
Ethyl α -methylcyclohexenyl acetate	" "	5	0.15
Ethyl α -phenylcyclohexenyl acetate	" "	72	0.996
Ethyl hexenoate	Kon, Linstead and Mac- lennan (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	92	153
Ethyl α -methyl- Δ^b -hexenoate	" "	95	151
Ethyl α -phenyl- Δ^b -hexenoate	" "	94.5	35.63

* The mobility of α -methylhexenoic acids as given by Linstead and MacLennan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2454) is 18.8. This seems to be in error. The value for mobility calculated from their experimental results given on page 2455 comes out to be 4.882.

It will be observed that the effect of α -phenyl group is to depress the mobility in all cases. When compared with the α -methyl group it will be seen that the depression by the α -phenyl group is more than that produced by the α -methyl group in the Δ^a - and Δ^b -hexenoic acids. In the cyclohexane series (acids and esters) the mobility is slightly greater in α -phenyl compounds than in α -methyl compounds.

It will be observed from the above table that the α -phenyl group shifts the equilibrium to the $\alpha\beta$ -side in the case of cyclohexene compounds and also in hexenoic acids, but in hexenoic esters there is no such marked effect. When compared with α -methyl compounds it will be seen that the extent of the shift of equilibrium to the $\alpha\beta$ -side is much greater in the case of α -phenyl compounds in cyclohexene series. It will be thus seen that the anomaly observed in the case of ethyl α -methylcyclohexenylacetate in shifting the equilibrium to the $\beta\gamma$ -side is non-existent with the α -phenyl group. In the case of hexenoic esters the effect of α -phenyl group and of α -methyl group on equilibrium is of the same order.

The polar effect of the phenyl group is supposed to be of the type + or - T, that is, it is able to furnish either electron accession to or recession from an adjacent carbon atom, according to the sign of the field required

at the seat of reaction. + T effect of a phenyl group may be considered negligible in this case since the electronic displacements are opposed to the charge distributing process, and therefore will not be called into play. -T effect of the phenyl group by tending to absorb the charge on the α -carbon atom should increase the mobility and should shift the equilibrium to the $\alpha\beta$ -side. The shift of the equilibrium to the $\alpha\beta$ -side observed during the course of the present investigation is, therefore, accounted for by -T effect. This view, however, is not in harmony with the depression of mobility.

It seems, therefore, better to regard the effect of α -phenyl group as a nonpolar group as Linstead has suggested (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2498). Then the depression of mobility and the shift of equilibrium to the $\alpha\beta$ -side will be accounted for by the steric and conjugative effects of the phenyl group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

α -Phenylcyclohexylideneacetic Acid.— α -Phenylcyclohexenol acetic acid was prepared by a modification of the method of Ivanoff and Spasoff (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1932, 49, 377). The modifications introduced were (i) the preparation of sodium salt of phenylacetic acid in aqueous solution instead of in alcoholic solution; (ii) the use of isopropyl bromide in place of isopropyl chloride, (iii) the use of a mixture of ether and benzene in place of ether; the last two modifications being necessary due to the high temperature of the laboratory. The yields were the same as those of Ivanoff and Spasoff.

α -Phenylcyclohexenolacetic acid (10 g.) was gently refluxed on a sand-bath for 3 hours with freshly distilled acetic anhydride (15 c.c.). Water was then added and acetic acid removed under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with a solution of sodium bicarbonate and extracted with ether to remove the neutral impurities. The sodium bicarbonate extract was acidified and the precipitated acid was filtered and washed. α -Phenylcyclohexylideneacetic acid (yield 50%), m. p. 134°, was soluble in benzene, petrol, ether, chloroform and alcohol and best crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine long needles. Its constitution was proved by oxidation to cyclohexanone and benzoic acid. The presence of benzoic acid in the oxidation product is no doubt due to the further oxidation of benzoylformic acid which must have been formed as the first oxidation product. The percentage of iodine absorbed by it under the standard conditions of Linstead and May (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2565) is 2.4. The silver and lead salts are insoluble and the barium and calcium salts are somewhat soluble in water. (Found: C, 77.50; H, 7.51; Equiv., 216. Ag in

the silver salt, 32.57. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 77.7; H, 7.46; Equiv., 216. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2Ag$ requires Ag, 33.43 per cent). The *anilide* was prepared either (i) by the action of aniline on the crude acid chloride and worked up in the usual manner or (ii) by heating the acid with aniline for 2 hours at 180°. It crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 146°. (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{20}H_{21}ON$ requires N, 4.81 per cent).

The *p-toluidide* similarly prepared melted at 115°. (Found: N, 4.65. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 4.59 per cent).

Oxidation of α -Phenylcyclohexylideneacetic Acid.—To a solution of the acid (2 g.) in a small quantity of sodium carbonate solution was added potassium permanganate (3.2 g.) dissolved in water (150 c.c.). After the oxidation was complete it was distilled in steam. The presence of *cyclohexanone* in the distillate was confirmed by the preparation of the semi-carbazone, m. p. 168°. The contents of the flask after the steam distillation were filtered and the filtrate concentrated and acidified. The acid thus obtained had m. p. 120° and was identified as benzoic acid by mixed m. p.

Preparation of α -Phenylcyclohexenylacetic Acid.—Ethyl α -phenylcyclohexenolacetate was prepared by esterifying α -phenylcyclohexenolacetic acid by Fischer-Speier's method and was crystallised from petroleum ether or dilute methyl alcohol in fine long needles, m. p. 71°. (Found: C, 73.20; H, 8.42. $C_{16}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 73.29; H, 8.39 per cent).

The results of dehydration of ethyl α -phenylcyclohexenolacetate by various dehydrating agents are given in the following table, the methods of procedure and working up being exactly the same as described by Kon and Nargund (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE II.

Reagent.	Yield of the unsaturated ester.	J.	$\beta\gamma$.
P_2O_5	70 %	34.6	95.0%
$SOCl_2$	65	32.0	80.0
$POCl_3$	65	25.0	56.0
$KHSO_4$	55	21.2	42.0

The column J in the above table indicates the % of iodine absorbed by the unsaturated ester fraction under the standard conditions of Linstead and May (*loc. cit.*). The last column shows the percentage of $\beta\gamma$ -isomeride in the unsaturated ester fraction as found with the help of the reference curve given on p. 744.

The results show that the maximum amount of $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated ester is obtained by the use of phosphorus pentoxide. The unsaturated ester fraction obtained by dehydrating ethyl α -phenylcyclohexenol acetate by phosphorus

pentoxide was hydrolysed in cold and the resulting acid purified by treatment with sodium bicarbonate solution. α -Phenylcyclohexenylacetic acid is soluble in ether, benzene and alcohol. It is best crystallised from petrol in long colourless needles, m.p. 107° - 8° . (Found: C, 76.90; H, 7.22; Equiv., 216.8; Ag in the silver salt, 34.05. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 77.7; H, 7.46 per cent; Equiv., 216.0. $C_{14}H_{15}O_2Ag$ requires Ag, 33.46 per cent).

The *anilide* was soluble in alcohol, ether, chloroform and benzene and was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 168° . (Found: N, 4.78. $C_{20}H_{21}ON$ requires N, 4.81 per cent).

The *p-toluidide* melted at 174° . (Found: N, 4.45. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 4.69 per cent).

Oxidation of α -Phenylcyclohexenylacetic Acid.—To a solution of the acid (6 g.) in a small quantity of caustic potash solution was added a solution of potassium permanganate (9.48 g.) in water (300 c.c.). After the oxidation was complete the precipitated manganese dioxide was filtered and the filtrate concentrated and acidified. The product thus obtained after recrystallisation from benzene melted at 98° and was identified as glutaric acid. The filtrate was extracted with ether and the recovered product had m.p. 152° and was identical with phenylmalonic acid.

α -Phenyl- Δ^{α} -hexenoic Acid.— α -Phenyl- β -hydroxyhexoic acid (10 g.) of Ivanoff and Nicoloff (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1932, 51, 1325) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) for 3 hours on a sand-bath and worked up in the usual way. α -Phenyl- Δ^{α} -hexenoic acid (yield 50 %) is soluble in ether, benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate, alcohol and petrol. It crystallises in long needles when its solution in petrol is cooled in ice, m.p. 70 - 71° . Silver, calcium, barium and copper salts are insoluble in water. (Found: C, 75.60; H, 7.40; Equiv., 190.3; Ag in silver salt, 36. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 75.78; H, 7.37 per cent; Equiv., 190.0. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2Ag$ requires Ag, 36.36 per cent).

The *anilide* crystallised from chloroform and petrol, m.p. 130° . (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{18}H_{19}ON$ requires N, 5.28 per cent).

The *p-toluidide* crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petrol, m.p. 210° . (Found: N, 5.02. $C_{19}H_{20}ON$ requires N, 5.0 per cent).

Oxidation of α -Phenyl- Δ^{α} -hexenoic Acid.—The acid (3.8 g.), just neutralised with caustic potash, was treated in cold with a solution of potassium permanganate (6.32 g.) in water (300 c.c.). After the oxidation was complete manganese dioxide was filtered off and the filtrate concentrated and acidified. The sticky mass which separated was crystallised from hot water, m.p. 121° and was identified as benzoic acid by mixed m.p. The filtrate was extracted with ether, dried and the substance recovered. A liquid having a

characteristic smell was obtained which was identified as butyric acid by its calcium salt.

α -Phenyl- Δ^b -hexenoic Acid.—Ethyl α -phenyl- β -hydroxyhexoate, prepared by the Fischer-Speier's method from the corresponding β -hydroxy-acid of Ivanoff and Nicoloff (*loc. cit.*) was a colourless liquid, b.p. $165^\circ/10$ mm., D_{25}^0 , 1.0236, and refractive index, 1.49514 at 33° . (Found: C, 71.05; H, 8.5. $C_{14}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 71.18; H, 8.47 per cent).

The effect of various dehydrating agents on ethyl α -phenyl- β -hydroxyhexoate is given in the following table, the conditions of experiments and working being the same as in the corresponding cyclohexane compound.

TABLE III.

Reagent.	Yield of the unsaturated ester.	J.	By.
P_2O_5	71%	33.0	95%
$SOCl_2$	60	3.7	5.0
$POCl_3$	50	2.6	4.0
$KHSO_4$	50	2.0	2.0

It is evident, therefore, that phosphorus pentoxide is the best reagent for dehydration. The unsaturated ester fraction obtained by the dehydration of ethyl α -phenyl- β -hydroxyhexoate by phosphorus pentoxide was hydrolysed in the cold and the crude unsaturated acid recovered in the usual manner. It was partially esterified and the pure ester obtained was then again hydrolysed in the cold and the acid recovered.

α -Phenyl- Δ^b -hexenoic acid is a liquid, b.p. $155^\circ/10$ mm. The acid became a solid crystalline mass when cooled in a freezing mixture and melted at about -15° . The barium and calcium salts are soluble and the silver and copper salts are insoluble. (Found: C, 75.65; H, 7.20; Equiv., 190.1; Ag in the silver salt, 36.01. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 75.78; H, 7.37 per cent; Equiv., 190.0. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2Ag$ requires Ag, 36.6 per cent).

The *anilide* was prepared by the method of Douglas Hardy (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 391). Aniline (2g.) was slowly added to a cooled solution of ethyl magnesium iodide, prepared from magnesium (0.5 g.), ethyl iodide (4 g.) and dry ether (30 c.c.). When the evolution of ethane ceased ethyl α -phenyl- Δ^b -hexenoate (1.5 g.) was added and the solution was warmed on a water-bath for 15 minutes. It was then decomposed with hydrochloric acid and the ether extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The solid recovered was recrystallised from benzene and petrol, m.p. 100° . It is

soluble in alcohol, ether, benzene and chloroform. (Found : N, 5.44. $C_{10}H_{10}ON$ requires N, 5.28 per cent).

Oxidation of α -Phenyl- Δ^3 -hexenoic Acid.—The acid (3.8 g.), just neutralised with caustic potash, was treated in the cold with a solution of potassium permanganate (6.32 g. in 300 c.c. of water). When the oxidation was complete, manganese dioxide was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated and acidified and distilled in steam. The distillate, which was acidic, was extracted with ether. The ether layer was dried and ether removed. The residue was identified as propionic acid by converting it into *p*-nitrobenzyl ester. The contents of the flask after steam distillation were extracted with ether and the ether removed when a solid was obtained, m.p. 152° , mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of phenylmalonic acid, $151-52^\circ$.

Equilibrium and Mobility of the Acids. Conditions of Mobility and Equilibrium. Calculations of Mobility and Methods of Estimation.

Mobility of the acids was determined under the standard conditions of Linstead (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2581) *viz.*, heating the acid (1 mol.) with 25% caustic potash (10 equiv.) on a boiling water-bath. These conditions were insufficient for determining the equilibrium in some cases, hence the mixture of the acid and caustic potash (proportion of the acid to caustic potash being the same as above) was boiled in a copper vessel. Experiments for determining the equilibrium were also made, in some cases, starting with mixtures of the acids.

The percentage of $\alpha\beta$ - and $\beta\gamma$ -form in a mixture of the acids could be determined by the iodometric methods of Linstead and May (*loc. cit.*). The iodine values of the pure acids (*J*) were first determined and then known mixtures of $\alpha\beta$ - and $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated acids were prepared and their iodine value (*J*) determined experimentally. A curve was then plotted with the iodine value (*J*) and the percentage compositions of the mixtures as co-ordinate. With the help of this curve, known as reference curve, it was possible to determine the percentage of $\alpha\beta$ - and $\beta\gamma$ -acids in a mixture recovered from the mobility and equilibration experiments.

Mobility (*M*) was calculated according to the formula,

$$M(K_1 + K_2) = \frac{2.3}{T} \log \frac{E}{E - X}$$

where *T* is the time in hours, *E* is the value of *X* at equilibrium and *X* is the change in the time *T*.

The half change period was calculated according to the formula,

$$\text{Half change period} = \frac{1}{K_1 + K_2} \log_e 2.$$

The results are summarised in the following tables.

TABLE IV.

α -Phenylcyclohexylideneacetic acid $\rightleftharpoons$ α -Phenylcyclohexenylacetic acid.

Time = 1 hour. Temperature = 25°.

Reference curve.

% of $\alpha\beta$	...	0	10	30	50	70	90	100
J	...	89'77	82'5	62'92	46'65	37'9	19'81	2'48

Determination of the point of equilibrium.

No. of expt.	Initial material.	Time.	Temp.	J.	$\alpha\beta$ as determined from Ref. curve.	Equilibrium.
1	$\alpha\beta$	6 hrs.	B.p.	5	96'5 %	
2	$\alpha\beta$	60	"	8'54	92'5	
3	$\beta\gamma$	6	"	87'77	2'5	
4	$\beta\gamma$	33	"	82'44	10	
5 Mixture	50% $\alpha\beta$	70	"	54'77	43	
6 Mixture	40% $\alpha\beta$	80	"	56'87	41	42% $\alpha\beta$
7 Mixture	42% $\alpha\beta$	70	"	55'8	42	

Determination of the Mobility.

						Mobility 10 ($K_1 + K_2$).
1	$\alpha\beta$	32	100°	3'19	98'5	0'0082
2	$\alpha\beta$	100	"	7'5	93'5	0'0128
3	$\beta\gamma$	60	"	88'0	2'5	0'0098
4	$\beta\gamma$	100	"	87'5	3	0'0078

Average mobility = 10 ($K_1 + K_2$) = 0'00954.

Half change period = 726 hours.

Equilibrium = 42% $\alpha\beta$,

TABLE V.

α-Phenyl-Δ^a-hexenoic acid $\rightleftharpoons$ α-Phenyl-Δ^b-hexenoic acid.

Time = 1 hour. Temperature = 30°.

Reference curve.

% of αβ	...	0	10	30	50	70	90	100
J	...	34.5	31.44	24.95	18.8	12.7	5.65	2.2

Determination of the Point of Equilibrium and Mobility.

No.	Acid.	Temp.	Time.	J	% of αβ as found from the Ref. curve.	Mobility 10 (K ₁ + K ₂).	Equilibrium.
1 [*]	αβ	100°	36 hours	5.2	92	0.2651	
2	αβ	..	100	8.5	87		
3 [*]	βγ	..	10	18.4	51	0.681	
4 [*]	βγ	..	36	13.57	67	0.408	
5 [*]	βγ	..	50	11.0	75	0.3957	
6	βγ	..	100	8.5	87		87% αβ

The mobility was calculated from the results marked with*.

Average mobility = $10 (K_1 + K_2) = 0.4874$
 Half change period = 14.21 hours.
 Equilibrium = 87% αβ.

Preparation of Esters.

Ethyl α-phenylcyclohexylideneacetate was prepared from the dry silver salt of the pure α-phenylcyclohexylideneacetic acid and ethyl iodide in the usual manner, b. p. 175°/12 mm., D₃₃^o, 1.03651, n_D^o at 33°, 1.52829 and J, the % of iodine absorbed under the standard conditions of Linstead and May (*loc. cit.*). (Found: [R_L]_D, 72.5, Calc. 71.2).

(Found: C, 78.6 ; H, 8.32. C₁₈H₂₀O₂ requires C, 78.69 ; H, 8.31 per cent).

Ethyl α-phenylcyclohexenyl acetate was prepared from the dry silver salt of the corresponding pure acid, b. p. 170°/12 mm., D₃₃^o, 1.0384, n_D^o at 33°, 1.5177. (Found: [R_L]_D, 71, Calc. [R_L]_D 71.2). (Found : C, 78.72 ; H, 8.32. C₁₈H₂₀O₂ requires C, 78.69 ; H, 8.31 per cent).

Ethyl α-phenyl-Δ^a-hexenoate, prepared from the dry silver salt, had b. p. 145-150°/12 mm., D₃₃^o, 0.99704 ; n_D^o at 33°, 1.50209. (Found: [R_L]_D

64.53, Calc. $[R_L]_D$, 64.29). (Found : C, 76.95 ; H, 8.4. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 77.05 ; H, 8.3 per cent).

Ethyl α -Phenyl- Δ^b -hexenoate.—The crude α -phenyl- Δ^b -hexenoic acid was subjected to partial esterification for 2 hours, the following quantities being used : 1 mol. of the acid, 230 c. c. of absolute alcohol and 100 c. c. of 1N-alcoholic hydrochloric acid. It was worked up as usual, b. p., $140^\circ/10$ mm. D_{25}° , 0.99604, n_D at 33° , 1.49712 ; (Found : $[R_L]_D$, 63.93, Calc. $[R_L]_D$, 64.29). (Found ; C, 76.96 ; H, 8.41. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 77.05 ; H, 8.3 per cent).

*Equilibrium and Mobility of Esters : Conditions of Mobility
and Equilibrium and Calculations of Mobility.*

The conditions used for mobility and equilibration experiments were those used by Kon and Linstead (*loc. cit.*). The mobility was calculated according to the formula given on page 743 but in this case T is expressed in minutes. Half change period was also calculated by the formula given on the same page.

Method of Estimation: Linstead and May's iodometric method was used throughout. Reference curve for the iodine value J and composition of mixtures was constructed as usual.

The results of equilibration and mobility experiments are given in the following tables.

TABLE VI.

Ethyl α -phenylcyclohexylidene acetate		$\rightleftharpoons$	Ethyl α -phenyl-cyclohexenyl acetate.					
<i>Reference curve.</i>								
Time = 1 hour. Temp. = 30° .								
% of $\alpha\beta$	...	0	10	30	50	70	90	100
J	...	37.6	32.94	29.2	23.85	18.0	10.44	5.8
<i>Determination of the Position of Equilibrium and Mobility.</i>								
No	Initial ester.	Time	Temp.	J.	% of $\alpha\beta$	Mobility, $K_1 + K_2$		
1	$\alpha\beta$	24 hours	25°	6.9	99.0	0.000258.		
2	$\alpha\beta$	100	"	12.2	84.0	0.000148.		
3	$\beta\gamma$	100	"	26.87	39.0	0.000130.		
4	Mixture 75% $\alpha\beta$	100	"	17.4	71.0	Equilibrium		
5	Mixture 70% $\alpha\beta$	100	"	16.4	73.0	72% $\alpha\beta$		
Average mobility = $(K_1 + K_2) \times 10^4 = 0.996$.								
Half change period = 6950.								
Equilibrium = 72% $\alpha\beta$								

TABLE VII

Ethyl α -phenyl- Δ^a -hexenoate $\rightleftharpoons$ Ethyl α -phenyl- Δ^b -hexenoate.

Reference curves.

Time = 1 hour. Temp_a = 30°.

% of $\alpha\beta$	...	0	10	30	50	70	90	100
J	...	34.63	31.6	26.17	19.4	12.2	5.5	1.56.

Determination of the Position of Equilibrium and Mobility.

No	Initial ester.	Time.	Temp.	J.	% of $\alpha\beta$	Mobility. $K_1 + K_2$
1	$\alpha\beta$	5 hours	25°	1.8	99.0	
2	$\alpha\beta$	24	"	3.1	95.0	
3	$\beta\gamma$	24	"	3.0	95.0	
4	$\beta\gamma$	10	"	8.1	82.0	0.003376
5	$\beta\gamma$	5	"	14.6	64.0	0.00376

Average mobility $(K_1 + K_2) \times 10^4 = 35.65$
 Half change period = 194.2
 Equilibrium = 95% $\alpha\beta$

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